

CENTRO DE INVESTIGACIONES
DE TRABAJO SOCIAL

ISSN 2244-808X
DL. pp 201002Z43506

PERSPECTIVA ACCIÓN Y

Revista de Trabajo Social

Vol. 15 No. 1
Enero - Marzo
2025

Universidad del Zulia

Facultad de Ciencias Jurídicas y Políticas
Centro de Investigaciones de Trabajo Social

Modelo basado en competencias para el desarrollo de cualidades personales y profesionales de los docentes

Elvir Akhmetshin¹, Ilyos Abdullayev², Artemiy Kozachek³, Olga Savinkova⁴,
Rustem Shichiyakh⁵

¹Kazan Federal University, Kazán, Rusia; Moscow Aviation Institute
(National Research University), Moscú, Rusia.

E-mail: elvir@mail.ru; ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2576-503X>.

²Urgench State University, Urgench, Uzbekistán.

E-mail: abdullayev.i.s@mail.ru; ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9601-7434>.

³Tambov State Technical University, Tambov, Rusia.

E-mail: avkozachek@list.ru; ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0004-4453-0377>.

⁴Voronezh State Academy of Sports, Voronezh, Rusia.

E-mail: savinkova.o.n@mail.ru; ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1147-0070>.

⁵Kuban State Agrarian University named after I.T. Trubilin, Krasnodar, Rusia.

E-mail: shichiyakh.r.a@mail.ru; ORCID: <http://orcid.org/0000-0002-5159-4350>.

Resumen. Este estudio presenta los fundamentos teóricos de un modelo basado en competencias para la formación de docentes universitarios. Partiendo de una revisión de la literatura científica, el documento analiza los conceptos de competencia y competencia clave, estableciendo que el proceso educativo innovador está llevando a que las competencias clave se conviertan en la base de este modelo. Desde los aspectos teóricos del problema, se caracteriza el modelo en el proceso educativo innovador de la educación superior. El modelo incluye competencias básicas y clave como componentes en la preparación de los docentes de educación superior para el proceso educativo innovador, siendo la competencia innovadora la principal. El modelo es una estructura teórica que determina los objetivos, principios, estructura, contenido y métodos para lograr las condiciones establecidas por las universidades para el desarrollo personal y profesional de los docentes en el contexto del proceso educativo innovador. Identifica los requisitos para los docentes universitarios, fundamenta las competencias básicas y clave, y las dota de contenido como parte de la estructura del modelo. El modelo presenta un sistema de componentes interconectados: competencias básicas y clave, cuyo dominio contribuye al desarrollo personal y profesional, aumentando la competitividad y movilidad profesional de los docentes de educación superior, atendiendo a los requisitos del proceso educativo innovador.

Palabras clave: modelo basado en competencias, profesor de enseñanza superior, competencias básicas, competencias clave, proceso educativo innovador.

Competency-based model for the development of teachers' personal and professional qualities

Abstract. This study presents the theoretical foundations of a competency-based model for the training of university teachers. Based on a review of the scientific literature, the paper analyzes the concepts of competence and key competence, establishing that the innovative educational process is leading key competencies to become the basis of this model. From the theoretical aspects of the problem, the model is characterized in the innovative educational process of higher education. The model includes basic and key competencies as components in the preparation of higher education teachers for the innovative educational process, with the innovative competence being the leading one. The model is a theoretical structure that determines the objectives, principles, structure, content, and methods to achieve the conditions established by universities for the personal and professional development of teachers in the context of the innovative educational process. It identifies the requirements for university teachers, substantiates the basic and key competencies, and fills them with content as part of the model's structure. The model presents a system of interconnected components: basic and key competencies, whose mastery contributes to personal and professional development, increasing the competitiveness and professional mobility of higher education teachers, in line with the requirements of the innovative educational process.

Key words: competency-based model, higher education teacher, basic competencies, key competencies, innovative educational process.

INTRODUCTION

In modern conditions, the specifics and creative nature of higher education teachers' work pose high requirements to the representatives of this profession (Turanin & Posokhova, 2023; Tutkova et al., 2024). The problem of training higher education teachers to work in an innovative educational environment and manage innovative educational processes gives rise to the critical issue of defining and developing the conceptual foundation of the competency-based model for university teachers (Aziyev et al., 2024; Shestitko et al., 2024). The concept of the model of a teacher is a theoretical construct that determines the purpose and principles of the model's development and implementation, its structure and content, and the methods of achieving the conditions set by universities for teachers' personal and professional development in the context of the innovative educational process.

In developing the model's components, it is first necessary to identify the requirements for the specialist – a higher education teacher performing various activities, including innovative activities (Bochkareva et al., 2020). Second, it is necessary to specify the required theoretical knowledge, practical skills, and abilities (competencies) (Dulzon & Vasileva, 2009). Readiness for innovative activity is the driving force behind a teacher's innovative stance (Ling et al., 2023). In terms of structure, it is a complex integrated formation covering various qualities, properties, knowledge, and personal skills, serving as a prerequisite for teachers' effective work, the maximum realization of their capabilities, and the development of their creative potential.

The model for university teachers should include professional and personal development because the harmonization of the profession is the basis of the vocational training system. The creative direction of pedagogical activity presupposes a scientific view of pedagogical phenomena and the multiplicity of their solutions, which requires the integration of social and personal educational strategies (Andrienko & Kalachikova, 2016). Professional competence is increasingly recognized as an integral characteristic of the teacher's personality; the issue of the higher education teacher's necessary competencies is relevant and timely.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Our analysis of scientific sources shows that an individual's competence in psychological and pedagogical science is described in connection with a wide range of theoretical and applied issues, directed mainly at the professional establishment, development, and self-improvement as a subject of professional activity in many studies (Frolov & Makhotin, 2004; Akmaeva & Zhukov, 2010; Ekimova & Voronina, 2020). The phenomenon of professional competence is investigated by many scholars whose primary focus is higher education teachers' training (Sharipov, 2010; Lopanova, 2015; Gazgireeva & Burniasheva, 2019). The fundamental grounds for the renewal of the higher education system, the vocational training of higher education teachers, the theoretical and methodological foundations of the development of university teachers' professionalism and professional culture, mastery, and competence are covered by V.P. Medvedev and Iu.G. Tatur (2007), O.P. Khodenkova (2016), and M.R. Ziganshina et al. (2018). The components of teachers' professional competence that ensure personal and professional self-development and self-improvement and determine its acmeological culture are covered by O.N. Krylova and O.B. Dautova (2016), I.A. Gazieva and A.A. Burashnikova (2023), and T.Iu. Poliakova and V.M. Prikhodko (2022). The essence, structure, and content of innovative competence are considered by O.B. Tomilin et al. (2007), E.B. Nastuev (2020), and N.E. Kopytova (2013). The attributes of teachers' innovative competence are presented by G.I. Boinchanu (2010); the factors contributing to the formation of innovative competence are investigated by G.R. Khusainova et al. (2022) and A.A. Muraveva and O.N. Oleinikova (2020).

Despite a considerable body of research into the various matters of competence, the issue of the competency-based model for university teachers in the innovative educational process remains understudied.

The study aims to characterize the competency-based model for teachers of the new formation in the innovative educational process of higher education.

METHODS

In accordance with the features of the competency-based model for teachers in the innovative educational process in universities, we employed a qualitative approach. The data were collected between January 15 and March 15, 2024 using an analysis of scientific literature on the research problem.

The first stage of the study involved selecting the source base represented by research papers published in journals indexed in Scopus and Web of Science. Relying on the analysis of the source base, we determined the theoretical foundations of the model.

At the second stage, based on the generalization of the analysis of the source base, we identified the basic and key competencies of a higher education teacher as constituents in the model.

RESULTS

Theoretical foundations of the model

In today's science, the concepts of competence and competency are the main categories of the new approach in education and have different interpretations (Table 1).

TABLE 1. Analysis of the concepts of competence and competency

Category	Definition	Source
Competence	The totality of personal qualities (value-meaning orientations, knowledge, skills, abilities) determined by the experience of human activity in a specific socially and personally significant sphere	R.I. Akmaeva and V.M. Zhukov (2010)
	Mastery of the corresponding competency, including personal attitude to the subject matter	F.V. Sharipov (2010)
	A set of features (characteristics) of the person allowing them to perform certain activities aimed at solving problems (tasks) in a certain industry with high quality	E.B. Nastuev (2020)
Competency	A set of interrelated semantic orientations, knowledge, skills, abilities, and experience of activity in relation to a certain range of real-life objects necessary for the implementation of personally and socially significant productive activities	N.V. Ekimova and M.M. Voronina (2020)
	The person's willingness to mobilize their knowledge, skills, and external resources for effective action in a particular life situation	O.P. Khodenkova (2016)
	A personal characteristic of a specialist connected to solving a certain type of professional tasks	O.N. Krylova and O.B. Dautova (2016)
	A general ability based on knowledge, experience, values, and aptitudes gained through learning	T.Iu. Poliakova and V.M. Prikhodko (2022)

Note: compiled based on (Akmaeva & Zhukov, 2010; Sharipov, 2010; Khodenkova, 2016; Krylova & Dautova, 2016; Ekimova & Voronina, 2020; Nastuev, 2020; Poliakova & Prikhodko, 2022).

The presented definitions make it clear that most researchers attribute to the structure of professional competence "a set of objectively necessary knowledge and skills to solve the problems of professional practice" (Nastuev, 2020:24). A.A. Muraveva and O.N. Oleinikova (2020) pay attention to the fact that the fashion for competencies without any analysis of the real needs of universities leads to models created without their further application. It is important to determine the purpose of designing a competency-based model from its inception. There is also the danger that the list of competencies considered necessary will grow infinitely long and eventually experience devaluation.

A purposeful literature review also suggests that the overwhelming majority of researchers believe that among the derivatives of the term “competence” (“professional competence”) are the concepts of key competencies, basic competencies, universal competences, etc. The context of our research requires us to characterize the concept of key competencies considering the features of teachers’ work in the innovative educational process. Most publications interpret key competencies as competencies common for all professions (Krylova & Dautova, 2016; Poliakova & Prikhodko, 2022). The mastery of key professional competencies by university teachers is an important task for the didactics of higher education. Analysis of the designed key competencies allows determining individual educational strategies, choosing adequate learning technologies, and establishing mechanisms for the assessment and self-assessment of the teacher’s readiness for effective scientific and educational work in the framework of the innovative educational process. The educational result of such an approach is a set of key competencies reflecting the personal and professional development of a higher education teacher.

The innovative educational process is leading to the establishment of the model of the new formation of teachers based on key competencies. In global educational practice, this concept is described as a priority. This owes, first, to the fact that key competencies combine the intellectual and skill-based components of education. Second, the concept of competency embodies the ideology of interpreting the content of education “from the result”. Third, a key competency is integrative, combining several homogeneous or related knowledge and skills. Key competencies are multifunctional, and mastering them can solve various problems in the professional or social spheres.

Competency model of a contemporary higher education teacher

We identified, substantiated, and provided content for the basic and key competencies in the structure of the professional competence of a higher education teacher. They form the foundation of the competency-based model of a new-age teacher. Under the concept of the model, we understand the system of interrelated components: basic and key competencies, which contribute to personal and professional development and increase the competitiveness and professional mobility of higher education teachers who meet the requirements of the innovative educational process.

This includes the following basic competencies (Table 2).

TABLE 2. Basic competencies of a higher education teacher

No.	Competency	Content
1	Theoretical and methodological	Mastery of the methodology of cognition and philosophical comprehension of the world as an integral system, knowledge of the scientific world picture Basic knowledge of sociology, ability to use the knowledge of society as a socioeconomic system and the history of its development in professional work Knowledge of the basics of anthropology, ability to use the knowledge of man in professional activities Understanding the goals and objectives of work, ability to see the problem and set and solve tactical and strategic objectives General scientific knowledge as a foundation for a profession or group of professions

TABLE 2. Continuación

No.	Competency	Content
2	Research	<p>Ability to observe how phenomena and processes occur and analyze them in terms of their content, causes, and consequences</p> <p>Ability to employ various research methods, hypothesize, design and conduct research, and work with information</p> <p>Participation in research projects, scientific and methodological seminars, and conferences with presentation of personal research results</p> <p>Ability to engage students and colleagues in scientific activities, performance of dissertation research, management of scientific research, and participation in the work of scientific councils and expert groups</p>
3	Psycho-pedagogical	<p>Knowledge of the basics of pedagogy and the theory and methods of vocational training</p> <p>Knowledge of the basics of psychology, mastery of elementary self-diagnostic and diagnostic methods</p> <p>Studying psychological and pedagogical literature, application of personality-oriented pedagogical technologies and psychological methods in professional teaching practice</p>
4	Methodological	<p>Ability to develop and edit educational and thematic plans and programs, methodological recommendations and didactic materials, syllabuses, control and assessment materials, and educational and methodological complexes</p> <p>Mastery of teaching methods for the relevant discipline, the ability to prepare and conduct training sessions and educational activities</p> <p>Ability to organize students' independent work and study methodological literature and promising pedagogical practices</p> <p>Generalization of personal pedagogical experience in different forms</p>
5	Subject	<p>In-depth knowledge of the content of the academic discipline, constant monitoring of scientific literature in the subject field, knowledge of the latest world achievements in teaching</p> <p>Attendance of advanced training courses, internships, training, participation in department meetings devoted to reviewing new content of the academic subject, participation in interdepartmental, university, and regional seminars, workshops, and conferences on the subject</p> <p>Ability to apply innovative methods and technologies in teaching the subject</p>

Note: developed by the authors.

The most important component in the model is key competencies (Table 3).

TABLE 3. Key competencies of a higher education teacher

No.	Competency	Content
1	Innovative	<p>Recognition of the social significance of innovations, involvement in social creativity, and ability to join in one or more stages of the innovation process</p> <p>Personal aptitude to master new things, readiness for changes in the methods of professional activity</p> <p>Innovative perception: perception of one's innovations and innovations or discoveries in general, ability to see new elements in the relatively constant and propose fundamentally new solutions to problems</p> <p>Creativity in solving professional problems</p> <p>Possession of special theoretical knowledge and practical skills in pedagogical innovations and the theory of innovative pedagogical activity, ability to effectively apply them in practice</p> <p>The use of updated, more effective forms, means, and methods of teaching and the achievement of qualitatively new results on this basis as a result of implementing innovations</p>
2	Commercial	<p>Terminological and normative-legal literacy in the commercial sphere, knowledge of copyright law and the transfer of intellectual products into intangible assets for higher education</p> <p>Understanding of the commercialization process, ability to position oneself as a subject in the market of innovative scientific and educational developments and services</p> <p>Initiative and entrepreneurship, ability to analyze the situation on the labor market, command of business language, ability to propose business ideas and find sources of funding for innovative scientific research</p>
3	Information technology	<p>Full and adequate provision of educational and other types of information to students to help them achieve their learning and other objectives</p> <p>Ability to search, analyze, transform, and apply information to solve professional problems</p> <p>Skills in working with information on academic subjects, educational specialties, and industries</p> <p>Ability to navigate the flow of scientific information and select the main information for professional activities</p> <p>Proficiency with modern technical support and information technology and information search, analysis, selection, transformation, storage, and transfer methods</p> <p>Knowledge of traditional and information technologies, mastery of information and communications methods and technologies for teaching and developing electronic educational and methodological complexes</p>
4	Project management	<p>Mastery of project management, ability to attract students and colleagues to project activities, readiness to model professional activity and educational trajectory</p> <p>Ability to mobilize intellectual and psychophysiological abilities to replenish knowledge, ability to design learning, plan the system of work, and predict the results</p> <p>Ability to adequately assess professional capabilities and performance and adjust practice</p>

TABLE 3. Continuación

No.	Competency	Content
5	Upbringing and development	Ability to develop one's own and students' research abilities and qualities; ability to foster the right beliefs, motives, values, and norms of behavior in oneself and students; general and professional culture, high moral qualities, corporate culture, and respect for the scientific and educational community
6	Communication and reflection	Awareness of all types of communication in professional practice Work to improve one's image (style) as a teacher, lecturing skills, knowledge of professional thesaurus, skills of working in professional pedagogical groups Participation in mass cultural and educational events Ability to cooperate effectively with other people and build subject-subject relations in the process of professional activity Proficiency in foreign languages

Note: developed by the authors.

DISCUSSION

At the present stage in the development of higher education, against the background of constantly accelerating information accumulation, the issue of the substantive content of the professional competencies of a higher education teacher has gained features that were previously not inherent to it. This is connected with the changing socio-professional function of a teacher, whose task is now not limited only to transferring the accumulated sum of knowledge (Gapsalamov et al., 2020). Given the increasing requirements for the training of a modern specialist, a teacher in higher education should focus on creating such organizational conditions of the innovative educational process that contribute to students' recognition of the need to independently acquire and modernize their knowledge and continuously work on self-development and self-improvement (Muraveva & Oleinikova, 2020; Archugova et al., 2023).

The basic knowledge, professional skills, and competencies of a higher education teacher cannot suffice for the entire duration of their multicomponent pedagogical career. The content of key competencies (Kopytova, 2013), which ensure the professional functioning and the professional development of teachers and their compliance with Russian and global trends and standards, is fundamentally changing.

There are grounds to speak not only of the competencies inherent to a specialist in a field, which constitute the basis of their professional skills, but also of the emergence of new competencies that still need to be mastered and whose content is not yet fully determined, but which are going to distinguish a person and a professional of the new formation.

The development of a competent higher education teacher is impossible without the support of the ideas of managing their professionalization. This relies on the principles of systematic, integral, synergetic, maneuverable, and forward-looking education. Developed based on basic and key competencies, the competency-based model of a higher education teacher can serve as a foundation for the theoretical and methodological bases to train higher education teachers to model the educational environment in the framework of the innovative educational process.

CONCLUSION

The competency-based model of a higher education teacher as a subject of pedagogical activity in the university educational space is multidimensional, corresponding to a complex of developed pedagogical abilities, personal abilities, skills, and theoretical and applied knowledge. The totality of their pedagogical abilities, personal abilities, and professional competencies helps a university teacher to organize pedagogical communication, carry out pedagogical interaction with students, achieve a high level of skill, and actively shape their own personality as a teacher.

The university educational space is an important condition and result of the activity of subjects in education. It provides the continuity of educational events and the transmission of social, moral, and spiritual experience. It reflects the system of real interactions between a teacher in higher education and the open social environment and interactions aimed at utilizing society's educational potential to meet their own educational and self-development needs.

We see further research prospects in the experimental verification of the theoretical model and the study of the mechanisms, conditions, and factors of organization of the innovative university educational space to develop and form the basic and key competencies of a higher education teacher.

BIBLIOGRAPHIC REFERENCES

- Akmaeva, R. I., & Zhukov, V. M. (2010). "Vozmozhnosti i problemy realizatsii kompetentnostnogo podkhoda v vysshem professionalnom obrazovanii" ["Opportunities and problems of the competency approach in higher vocational education"]. **Vestnik of Astrakhan State Technical University. Series: Economics**, 1, 123-130.
- Andrienko, A. V., & Kalachikova, O. N. (2016). "Razrabotka modeli kompetentsii prepodavatelei vuza dlia zadach upravleniia personalom" ["Competency model professor university: Impact on human resources"]. **University Management: Practice and Analysis**, 101 (1), 10-16.
- Archugova, A., Bolotina, N., Dugina, T., & Kartseva, E. (2023). "Development of a system for assessing the quality of the work of university research and teaching staff to improve the educational environment". **Revista Conrado**, 19 (95), 416-422.
- Aziyev, A., Shalgynbayeva, K., Aitysheva, A., & Alpyssov, A. (2024). "Impact of psychological training on the development of professionally important qualities of an educational psychologist". **European Journal of Contemporary Education**, 13 (1), 5-13. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13187/ejced.2024.1.5>
- Bochkareva, T. N., Akhmetshin, E. M., Zekiy, A. O., Moiseev, A. V., Belomestnova, M. E., Savelyeva, I. A., & Aleynikova, O. S. (2020). "The analysis of using active learning technology in institutions of secondary vocational education". **International Journal of Instruction**, 13 (3), 371-386. <http://dx.doi.org/10.29333/iji.2020.13326a>
- Boinchanu, G. I. (2010). "Formirovanie innovatsionnoi kompetentnosti prepodavatelii vysshogo uchebnogo zavedeniia sistemy MVD Rossii" ["Formation of innovative competence of the teacher of the higher educational institution of system of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of Russia"]. **RUDN Journal of Informatization in Education**, 3, 44-50.

- Dulzon, A. A., & Vasileva, O. M. (2009). “Model kompetentsii prepodavatel'ia vuza” [“Competency model of university teachers”]. **University Management: Practice and Analysis**, 2, 29-37.
- Ekimova, N. V., & Voronina, M. M. (2020). “Kompetentsii sovremennogo prepodavatel'ia vuza” [“Modern university teachers' competences”]. **Educational Resources and Technologies**, 32 (3), 22-27. <https://doi.org/10.21777/2500-2112-2020-3-22-27>
- Frolov, Iu. V., & Makhotin, D. A. (2004). “Kompetentnostnaia model kak osnova kachestva podgotovki spetsialistov” [“Competency model as a basis for assessing the quality of specialist training”]. **Higher Education Today**, 8, 34–41.
- Gapsalamov, A. R., Akhmetshin, E. M., Sharipov, R. R., Vasilev, V. L., & Bochkareva, T. N. (2020). “Approaches to information security in educational processes in the context of digitalization”. **TEM Journal**, 9 (2), 708-715. <http://dx.doi.org/10.18421/TEM92-38>
- Gazgireeva, L. Kh., & Burniasheva, L. A. (2019). “Professionalno-pedagogicheskaiia kompetentnost prepodavatel'ia vuza kak kliuchevoi faktor povysheniia kachestva obrazovaniia” [“Professional and pedagogical competence of the teacher of higher education institution as key factor for improvement of education quality”]. **Humanities and Social Sciences**, 4, 235-243. <https://doi.org/10.23683/2070-1403-2019-75-4-235-243>
- Gazieva, I. A., & Burashnikova, A. A. (2023). “Kompetentnostnyi funktsionalnyi profil prepodavatel'ia vuza: Tsennostnyi podkhod” [“Competency functional profile of the university teacher: Value approach”]. **Higher Education in Russia**, 32 (3), 26-47. <https://doi.org/10.31992/0869-3617-2023-32-3-26-47>
- Khodenkova, O. P. (2016). “Model kliuchevykh kompetentsii prepodavatel'ia vuza, formiruemaia pod vlianiem poslevuzovskogo obrazovaniia” [“Model of key competences of the high school staff, formed under the influence of post-graduate education”]. **Vestnik of Astrakhan State Technical University. Series: Economics**, 2, 169-173.
- Khusainova, G. R., Karstina, S. G., & Galikhanov, M. F. (2022). “Otsenka gotovnosti prepodavatelei k innovatsionnoi professionalno-pedagogicheskoi deiatelnosti” [“Assessing educators' readiness for innovative professional and pedagogical activities”]. **Higher Education in Russia**, 31 (7), 42-60. <https://doi.org/10.31992/0869-3617-2022-31-7-42-60>
- Kopytova, N. E. (2013). “Innovatsionnye kompetentsii prepodavatel'ia vuza” [“Innovative competencies of a university teacher”]. **Psychological-Pedagogical Journal “Gaudeamus”**, 1 (21), 28-32.
- Krylova, O. N., & Dautova, O. B. (2016). “Profil kompetentsii” prepodavatel'ia vysshei shkoly kak instrument ego professionalnogo razvitiia” [“Competency profile” of a higher education teacher as a tool for their professional development”]. **Pedagogika**, 3, 105-110.
- Ling, P., Isaeva, N., Bolzan, N., Kolganov, S., Chirich, I., & Zhabchik, S. (2023). “Motivación estudiantil en humanidades: Su impacto en el rendimiento académico y desarrollo profesional” [“Student motivation in humanities: Its impact on academic performance and professional development”]. **Interacción y Perspectiva**, 14 (1), 230-243. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10456690>.
- Lopanova, E. V. (2015). “Professionalno-pedagogicheskaiia kompetentnost prepodavatel'ia VUZA: Struktura, sodержanie, otsenka sformirovannosti” [“Professional and pedagogical competence of university teacher: Structure, content and assessment of maturing”]. **Scientific Review. Pedagogical Science**, 2, 121-121.

- Medvedev, V. P., & Tatur, Iu. G. (2007). “Podgotovka prepodavatel'ia vysshei shkoly: Kompetentnostnyi podkhod” [“Training higher education teachers: The competency approach”]. **Higher Education in Russia**, 11, 46-56.
- Muraveva, A. A., & Oleinikova, O. N. (2020). “Kompetentsii prepodavatelei vuzov: Sovremennye vyzovy i smena paradigmy” [“Competences of university teachers: Contemporary challenges and change of paradigm”]. **Pedagogy and Psychology of Education**, 3, 100-115. <https://doi.org/10.31862/2500-297X-2020-3-100-115>
- Nastuev, E. B. (2020). “Struktura professionalnoi kompetentnosti prepodavatel'ia vysshei shkoly v obespechenii kachestva obrazovaniia” [“Structure of professional competence of a higher education teacher in ensuring the quality of education”]. **Scientific Review. Pedagogical Science**, 3, 23-27.
- Poliakova, T. Iu., & Prikhodko, V. M. (2022). “Kompetentsii prepodavatel'ia tekhnicheskogo vuza v Rossii i za rubezhom” [“Technical university teacher competences in Russia and abroad”]. **Higher Education in Russia**, 31 (7), 61-78. <https://doi.org/10.31992/0869-3617-2022-31-7-61-78>.
- Sharipov, F. V. (2010). “Professionalnaia kompetentnost prepodavatel'ia vuza” [“Professional adequacy of university’s pedagogue”]. **Higher Education Today**, 1, 18-24.
- Shestitko, I., Zhuzeyev, S., Polyakova, G., Kozachek, A., Galizina, E., & Panova, E. (2024). “Effect of pedagogical support on the development of linguocultural competence among students in multi-ethnic groups”. **Revista Conrado**, 20 (97), 506-512.
- Tomilin, O. B., Kochugaev, P. N., Sukharev, L. A., & Masserova, N. N. (2007). “Kompetentsii akademicheskogo i administrativnogo personala universiteta i innovatsionnaia deiatel'nost'” [“Competences of academic and administrative University staff and innovative activity”]. **University Management**, 1, 53-61.
- Turanin, V., & Posokhova, Y. (2023). “El impacto de la transformación digital en la sociedad y el derecho a la educación” [“Digital transformation’s impact on society and the right to education”]. **Interacción y Perspectiva**, 14 (1), 211-220. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10440273>.
- Tutkova, I., Kudaiberdieva, G., & Kozhobekov, K. (2024). “Training of pedagogical staff in the context of digital didactics”. **Revista Conrado**, 20 (96), 279-283.
- Ziganshina, M. R., Karandashov, S. A., & Mendelson, V. A. (2018). “Pedagogicheskaia kompetentnost prepodavatel'ia vysshei shkoly” [“Pedagogical competence of a teacher in higher school”]. **Engineering Education**, 23, 165-168.